

Green Political Theory and Hindi Cinema

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Green political theory has recently emerged as a vibrant approach to understand politics, society, culture and economics. Green political theory is an ideology that seeks to combine environmentalism, non-violence, social justice, grass-root democracy and feminism to create an ecologically sustainable society. The proposed paper intends to apply green political theory to analyze environmental consciousness in Hindi cinema. As such, there is no genre of environmental cinema in Bollywood. Yet, from the very beginning, Bollywood cinema has opposed merciless exploitation of nature, unbridled capitalism, urbanisation and big industrial projects in the name of development. Themes of environmentalism, sustainable development and rights of tribal are woven in the stories of Hindi cinema.

Green Political Theory: Establishing Contours

Green Political Theory (GPT) is one of the most vibrant political theories which is attracting the worldwide attention. Although environmentalism itself is an age-old phenomenon but GPT is a wider term that includes environmentalism and many other ideas. In fact, there is no doubt that environmentalism is the most important part of GPT. But GPT claims that its concerns go beyond just environmentalism. GPT is essentially a political ideology which intends to create a society which is ecologically sustainable, and centered around non-violence, social justice, feminism and participatory democracy with a responsible ruling elite and collective rights and responsibilities. It champions individual rights but opposes unbridled capitalism which justifies itself on the basis of individual rights. Many proponents of GPT add that the rule of law, responsible press, aware citizenry which would never compromise on the issue of sustainable development, a commitment to keep environmental issues on the forefront of political agenda and foreign policy based upon the advocacy of environmental protection and support to climate control treaties are also the hallmarks of GPT.

After going through various arguments we can underscore few basic points of GPT—

- 1-a call for inter-generational justice
- 2-a belief in democratic means
- 3-goal of ecological sustainability and environmentalism
- 4-stress on women rights
- 5-democracy based upon collective rights and responsibilities
- 6-an opposition to unbridled capitalism
- 7-end of feudalism and farmers' rights on their land
- 8-ecological issues on the forefront of political agenda
- 9-Gandhian belief in village empowerment, respect for hard work, capitalism with trusteeship theory and stress on cottage industry

Hindi Cinema and Green Political Theory

As mentioned earlier that there is no specific genre of environmental cinema in India but Hindi films from very beginning have portrayed the various aspects of GPT. However various facets of GPT are natural to Indian culture, society and polity. This is the reason that they are portrayed in an indirect manner in Hindi films. This paper will undertake the case studies of *Do Bigha Zamin* (1953) and *Chakravyuha* (2012) to argue that although the cinema of 1950s portrayed the elements of GPT in a very poignant manner, the portrayal is becoming aggressive in the cinema of new millennium. The new age cinema portrays frustration of people with governments and big business which promote big ticket industrial reforms in the name of development and pay only lip service to issues raised by GPT. Cinema of new millennium even advocates violent strategies for attaining the various goals of GPT, like land rights, sustainable development and opposition to unbridled capitalism.

Case Study-1

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Do Bigha Zamin (Two Acres of Land): A Farmer's Lost Battle to Maintain Ownership of his Land

For long, critics have praised *Do Bigha Zamin* as a milestone in Hindi cinema.ⁱ On the face of it, it is the story of a farmer Shambhu Mahto (Balraj Sahni), a lower caste farmer, who has been hit badly by Bengal famine. The real reason of his sorrow is that the local landlord (Murad), wants to acquire his land on the pretext that Shambhu had taken a loan from him. The landlord desires to build a factory in the village and Shambhu's two-acre land is pivotal to his design. Shambhu has to pay back the landlord in three months and hence he leaves his wife Paro (Nirupa Roy) behind and moves to Calcutta to look for some other source of money. His son Kanhaiya (Rattan Kumar) accompanies him. There he faces problems of a different magnitude. His belongings get stolen. He can't find a job and his son falls sick. He ends up as a rickshaw puller. His son starts working as shoe shiner. A person asks him to chase another rickshaw carrying his girlfriend. He keeps on offering him more and more money for running faster. It results in an accident in which Shambhu is badly hurt. Kanhaiya writes a letter to his mother and asks her to come immediately to Calcutta. An evil person entraps her in the garb of knowing the address of Shambhu. When she runs away, she is hit by a car. Shambhu spends all his savings in her treatment. When Shambhu, his wife Paro and son Kanhaiya return to the village, they discover that their land already been auctioned and a factory has been built on his land. Shambhu wistfully watches the smoke from the chimney of the factory. A metaphor for his small dreams going into thin air.ⁱⁱ In a heart-wrenching scene, he tries to take a handful of soil from his land but watchman scolds him and calls him a thief. Thus he is not even allowed to carry even a handful of soil from his two acres of land.

Bimal Roy, the director and producer of *Do Bigha Zamin* is considered as the vanguard of neo-realistic cinema in India. The film does not talk about environment directly but it closely adheres to social aspects of GPT by using metaphors, symbols and subtly coded messages. Film begins with the shots of parched land and a voiceover informs, "There has been a famine for two years. Even the leaves of trees are dried. There is a pandemonium in the country." Opening shot clearly shows catastrophic effects of no rains. Pandemonium in the country depicts social and political concern over drought. Then heavy showers drench the village. Environmental consciousness is related with economic well being and sexuality also. Scenes of people dancing in the rain stress upon the communitarian character of rural India. In the rain dance, Shambhu dances with his wife. One of the villager comments, "Shambhu has been married for ten years, still he is so romantic." Another villager replies in a sarcastic tone, "What would you know, you only know how to beat your wife." This scene gives a message that wife beating is something to be looked down upon and women are to be cherished. In later parts also, film depicts strong women characters and gives the message of women empowerment. In an important scene, local landlord comes in his car with urban investors. They want to construct a factory there and the only problem is Shambhu's two acres of land. Landlord's friends say, "We will name it as Great Janta Mills. Money begets money. Government is bent upon finishing feudalism. Why should we not look towards industry? One day this village will become an advanced city. There will be electricity and there will be dance parties. Many gentlemen and ladies will come here." This is one of the finest critique of India's first Prime Minister Nehru's concept of development and industrialization. Landed aristocracy is trying to turn itself into a new bourgeois class. Urbanization is taken as symbol of development. Forces of unbridled capitalism are unleashed. It is ironical that the landlord's friends plan to name it as Janta mills because Janta in Hindi language, means common people. Thus it is a strategy of capitalism that it presents itself as benefactor of people. Shambhu is pressured by landlord to sell his piece of land. Shambhu clearly says, "Land is my mother. Does anyone sell his mother?" This is a direct reference to environmental consciousness in which a farmer says he will never sell his piece of land. Landlord goes to court to claim that Shambhu has taken loan from him and is not willing to return it. So he should be allowed to auction Shambhu's land. In the court Shambhu is laughed upon. He keeps on saying that his loan was only 65 rupees. Landlord has forged the paper and swelled the loan up to 235 rupees. Court orders that landlord cannot takeover Shambhu's land just like that. However, Shambhu will have to pay the loan within three months. Shambhu and Kanhaiya come to Calcutta. While leaving the village behind, haunting visuals of farms make them cry. When they reach Calcutta, a person tells them, "This city will give you nothing. Whatever you have, it will snatch that also away." A dominant woman, who owns a building, gives shelter to Shambhu and helps him at various points. In one of the most poignant scenes of Hindi cinema, when Shambhu, along with his wife and son comes back to village, he finds that a factory has already been constructed on his two acres of land. Kanhaiya says, "Look mother, where steam is coming out from chimney, our house was exactly at that spot." When Shambhu tries to take a handful of soil from his erstwhile land and is stopped by guard, Bimal Roy gives a clear message that in the name of development, all rights have been snatched away from poor.

Chakravyuha: Poor Fight Back with Guns

Chakravyuha literally means a labyrinth with no clear sense of right and wrong. Adil Khan (Arjun Rampal), a highly decorated police officer is posted to Nandighat, after a horrifying massacre of 84 policemen. Adil's wife Rhea Menon (Esha Gupta) is also a police officer. Within days, he discovers that the Maoists, led by the ruthless and charismatic Rajan (Manoj Bajpai), effectively control the area. They are able to swiftly thwart Adil's most determined efforts. Despite holding a position of enormous power as the SSP of Nandighat, Adil has never felt so helpless in his career. But then, into his life, re-enters Kabir (Abhay Deol). Rootless, aimless, the quintessential rolling stone. His only anchor in life has always been his friendship with Adil and Rhea. They were in police academy together but Kabir walks out in the middle of his training because he could not tolerate senior officers misbehaving with juniors. Kabir proposes an outrageous plan: He will infiltrate Rajan's group and be Adil's informer, and together they will smash the Maoist organization in Nandighat. In spite of his apprehensions, Adil agrees.

Kabir is able to infiltrate Naxalites and craftily wins their confidence. He secretly begins informing Adil, who starts attacking the Maoists with great success. An enormous cache of arms is raided; two top national leaders and 63 activists are killed at an arms-training camp, and Rajan himself is captured. Within weeks, Adil-Kabir turn the game, pushing the Maoists onto the back foot.

But Kabir also begins discovering a different reality: The abject helplessness of the rural poor, brutally displaced in the name of development, the fruits of which never reach them; their land, their forest, their water snatched by their own government to allow big business to exploit the area and its people further. As the poverty and desperation rise, so does a cry of anger, giving birth to the Naxalites who believes the only way to counter this is with a gun. Then there is a nexus between politicians and industrialists. Mahanta group wants to establish an industrial complex in the area and for this land of 230 villages is required. Government has signed a contract with the Mahanta group and this is the real reason politicians want Naxalite movement defeated. Once Adil is able to control the area, he is asked by politicians, bureaucrats and officers from Mahanta group to get 230 villages vacated. When he refuses point blank because it is illegal, then he is removed of his responsibilities and Mahanta group unleashes private militias on helpless tribal. Now Adil and Kabir realize the real objectives of state supported terror. Kabir starts getting close to the activists. and he begins identifying with them: Rajan; Babu; Venu; and Juhi (Anjali Patil), a dedicated revolutionary with a tender heart, who has faced exploitation since her childhood. She begins to fall in love with Kabir. The confusion in Kabir's heart intensifies dangerously until he is on the horns of a ghastly dilemma: Who does he support now? Who does he fight? He finds himself in a chakravyuh (labyrinth) from which there is no retreat now. Although, Adil realizes the real motives of politicians, he wants to resolve it as a law and order problem. Before Kabir can make one last desperate attempt to resolve this with his friend Adil, events hurtle him into making choices that would put him at war with him. In the end Kabir and Juhi are shot dead by Adil while they are trying to lure the police on their track while Rajan and other naxalites escape.ⁱⁱⁱ

Similarities and difference between *Do Bigha Zamin* and *Chakravyuha*, released almost 60 years apart from each other, are nothing short of astounding. Land remains the most contested resource in both films and plight of the poor remains unchanged.^{iv} Another striking difference is that poor are willing to fight back with violent means. Gandhian values of non-violence and tolerance have been replaced by violent means of fighting for one's rights.

Film repeatedly gives the message that a brutal coalition of state, capitalists and police has forced poor tribal to take up arms. If there is somebody honest like Adil, he is used by state and then sidelined. When Adil protects villagers from private militias, he is told by his seniors that it is no longer his jurisdiction. Film makes a reference to Gandhi also. When Adil says that by killing Naxalites, he was just doing his job, his wife Rhea responds, "Oh a Gandhi with a gun." Thereby film laments the fact that neither Naxalites nor state believe in Gandhian method of non-violence. In the end, Kabir is also shot dead and state obviously wins.

GPT, *Do Bigha Zamin* and *Chakravyuha*

A content analysis and discourse analysis posit that both films closely follow the norms of GPT.^v While *Do Bigha Zamin* is closer to social aspects of GPT, *Chakravyuha* is unabashedly political and it sometimes goes against the pacifist values of GPT to attain environmental justice. This is nobody's argument that Roy and Jha studied GPT first to make their movies. This paper only argues that concerns of GPT are natural to the psyche of Indian filmmakers just like the rest of Indian society. Ethos of environmentalism are inherent part of Indian society and culture.^{vi}

Conclusion and Suggestions

GPT is an important idea to understand society, polity, economy and fight for environmental justice. Now the question is, what role cinema could play in the fight for environmental justice.^{vii} Although, it's not entirely true that there is no genre of environmental cinema in India. In 1989, Indian government's ministry of information and broadcasting set up a national award for best film on environmental conservation. A total of 18 awards have been given away in this category. But not a single Hindi film has won this award. These awards are always won by regional cinema. It again proves the need for the genre of environmental cinema in Hindi films. And it is Hindi films which yield massive socio-economic influence in India. Indian government can constitute an award for best Hindi film in the category of environmental protection and conservation. For making this kind of cinema reach to the masses, exemption in entertainment tax can be granted. The idea should be to make environmentally conscious films which are entertaining and part of commercial mainstream. There is a need to encourage this kind of cinema.^{viii} Then Cinema could play an important role in bringing environmental consciousness to Indian masses.

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